

MOTHER TERASA COLLEGE OF AGRICULTURE
(Affiliated to TAMIL NADU AGRICULTURAL UNIVERSITY)

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ABSTRACT *Compendium*

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Technologies for Resource Conservation in Crop Production

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The agricultural resources that are naturally available are soil, water, and nutrients. There are a variety of agricultural, technical, and other techniques that may be used to conserve these resources. Some agronomic strategies to save soil and water include contour cultivation, strip cropping, fallowing, mulching, tillage practises, crop rotation, intercropping, and cover cropping. Conservation agriculture (CA) is an agricultural strategy that helps preserve arable land while restoring damaged areas. CA also benefits farmers by lowering cultivation costs through labour, time, and farm power savings and improving and stabilising yields with less input use (fertilisers and pesticides). Tillage is the mechanical manipulation of soil to generate an edaphic environment suitable for crop development, infiltration capacity maintenance, aeration, and weed control. It is one of the types of soil, water, nutrient, crop, and pest management strategies. Conventional tillage is a strategy that relies heavily on cultivation for seedbed preparation and weed control. The traditional tillage approach is often seen as increasing the danger of erosion, hastening organic matter decomposition, and weakening soil structure. As a result, in some parts of the world, conventional tillage is giving way to novel conceptions of conservation tillage. Conservation tillage is commonly used in Western nations to prevent soil and water loss by minimum cultivation, which results in a considerable amount of plant leftovers on the soil surface. Modern conservation tillage technologies include reduced tillage, rotational tillage, minimum tillage, zero tillage, stubble mulch tillage, ridge tillage, and surface sowing.

Keywords: *resource; conservation; tillage; agriculture*